

Human Rights in Serving Imprisonment Penalty in Vietnam

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to study the current situation of ensuring human rights in the implementation of imprisonment penalty in Vietnam. The results show that Vietnamese law always attaches great importance to human rights for all prisoners. Inmates are always entitled to healthy activities, updated knowledge, labor training, sports and special amnesty to encourage prisoners to improve better.

Keywords: Human rights, imprisonment penalty, Vietnam

1. Introduction

Human rights and human rights guarantee have been and are the top concerns of the international community as well as of each country, including Vietnam. Ensuring human rights expresses the common viewpoints of modern states on construction and development, in which people and human rights are at the center. Also according to the prevailing view of states in ensuring human rights, special attention should be paid to at-risk groups, including prisoners serving sentences in prisons.

In Vietnam, human rights have long been recognized in the political disciplines, the Party's lines, undertakings and policies, and are institutionalized in the laws of the State. In line with the Party's line and policies, Vietnam has actively participated in international human rights treaties of the United Nations, including Conventions on the protection of human rights of prisoners such as Cong. International Covenant on civil and political rights in 1966; International Covenant on economic, cultural and social rights in 1966; The 1985 Convention against Torture, Inhuman Treatment and Humiliation ... The provisions relating to the protection of human rights of prisoners in these conventions have been internalized into the provisions of Constitution 2013, Criminal Procedure Code 2015, Penal Code 2015 (amended in 2017) and especially Law on Execution of Criminal Judgments in 2019. In general, in legal documents In this case of Vietnam, international human rights standards of prisoners have been fully and specifically recognized, reflecting Vietnam's efforts to internalize international rights standards. people enter the national legal system.

However, some contents of the rights and the mechanism to ensure the rights of prisoners in the current Vietnamese law are still incomplete or not really consistent with the international legal standards of human rights that Vietnam. Male sign, join. The legal document system in this area is overlapping and lacks of guiding documents for uniform implementation. As a result, it is still difficult to secure some of the rights of inmates in the execution of the imprisonment penalty. Inmates management, detention, detention and education in some prisons is not really tight; The regime of the inmates' diet, clothing, accommodation, activities, communication and communication regimes in some places are not really ensured ... These shortcomings and shortcomings have adversely affected the quality and performance results of the work of educating and improving prisoners, therefore, it is necessary to find solutions to overcome the above limitations. This is because ensuring human rights is one of the basic goals and criteria for the building of the Socialist State of Vietnam. In addition, in the context of Vietnam's increasingly deepening international integration, the issue of ensuring human rights in general and human rights in the execution of imprisonment in particular is increasingly gaining international public opinion and in water attention, monitoring. Any violation of the offender's rights, whether for an objective or subjective cause, resulting from inadequacies in policies, laws or the limitations of the enforcement organization, may lead to criticism. of public opinion at home and abroad, affecting and damaging the image and reputation of the State in international forums, and even negatively affecting Vietnam's international integration process.

The issue of ensuring human rights of prisoners has been studied a lot around the world, but still little is known in Vietnam. Although a number of scientific works on human rights guarantee of prisoners have been published, but mainly in the form of articles, dissertations or scientific topics at the grassroots or ministerial level. In addition, most of the researches mentioned were done before the 2013 Constitution, the 2015 Criminal Procedure Code, 2015 Penal Code (amended in 2017) and the Law on Execution of Criminal Judgments. The year 2019 - are the foundation documents in this field in Vietnam. In other words, there are currently no in-depth, comprehensive and up-to-date studies on ensuring human rights of inmates in serving prison sentences in Vietnam.

2. Literature review

2.1. The group has a theoretical research on ensuring human rights in the execution of imprisonment penalty

In the sixth part of the book "Comments on Criminal procedure code" by Geo L.J. Ann, 2013, offender's rights are mentioned and clarified. The author asserts that penalties and imprisonment allow for legal, certain restrictions on civil liberties and constitutional rights. Simultaneously with such restrictions, the offender must also be recognized for other human rights, and guaranteed to enjoy the rights consistent with the conditions of the place of custody. With a wide scope of research, covering all fields of imprisonment enforcement in terms of human rights approaches, this is an essential reference for the study of theoretical content in the topic. research talent.

Regarding the article, the magazine must include the article by Susan Easton titled "Protecting Prisoners: The Impact of International Human Rights Law on the Treatment of Prisoners in the United Kingdom" (roughly translated as Protecting Prisoners: The Impact of International human rights law for offenders in the UK In this article, the author examines the impact of international human rights law and standards on the protection of offenders in the UK, with specific reference The European Convention on Human Rights, which is associated with British law under the 1998 Human Rights Act. Accordingly, the contents of the Convention clearly stipulate the human rights to which offenders enjoy, however the scope of these rights will be limited by prison conditions as well as public attitudes toward prisoners, and the author argues that respect for the rights of inmates can contribute to uplifting prison standards and their responsibilities. specialized agencies in the process of implementing their tasks [156] This research has helped the postgraduate have a view an overview of prisoners' rights in the British criminal justice system, from which there is a basis to approach research on human rights in prison enforcement in Vietnam in terms of comparative law.

John C. Mubangizi made his remarks on criminal rights in his article "International human rights protection for prisoners: Which way South Africa?" (roughly translated as The protection of criminals in international human rights: Which path for South Africa?), 2001. The article focuses on the perspective of protecting human rights at the international level, examining the rights of prisoners. how to be protected at the international level and guidance for achieving certain standards in de facto protection of offender rights from South Africa. However, the author notes that international law prohibits actions related to human rights violations and fundamental freedoms for prisoners such as mistreatment, beating, and discrimination in institutions. detention, thereby requiring the stakeholders involved to respect the dignity and honor of the imprisoned [143]. The article is a useful reference for graduate students in understanding the theory of prisoners' rights, ensuring prisoners' rights in the execution of imprisonment sentences. This is a premise theoretical basis for the research author to continue to analyze in depth the theoretical basis of human rights in the execution of imprisonment penalty and the theoretical starting point measures to ensure that the assume the power of the person serving the imprisonment penalty in Vietnam.

Same approach with John C. Mubangizi, author Gerard de Jonge through the article "Prionners '(Human) rights and prisoners' litigation in the Netherlands" gives the author's opinion on the concepts of imprisonment and the execution of the prison sentence, outlines the rules that allow inmates to oppose the individual decisions of the

prison. At the same time, the author also describes the prison system in the Netherlands and the Prison Law, which lists a number of criminal cases in the Dutch courts and the European Court of Human Rights in France [138].

The article "Toward a Theory of Prisoners 'Rights'" (roughly translated as "Towards the theory of the rights of prisoners"), author Richard L. Lippke, 2002. This article explores the issue of prisoners' rights. The conditions of persons held in prison include both the psychological and physical problems caused by incarceration. In addition, the study also raises discussions around the issue of the nature of prisoners' basic civil rights. The author of the article hypothesizes whether the offender in the process of being detained will be deprived of all his civil rights or only some of the rights will be deprived; Whether or not the State has any obligation to facilitate the exercise of their remaining rights are specific rights that the offender cannot be deprived of or enjoy [152]. Articles with reference value related to giving the concept of human rights of offenders in the theoretical content of the study.

Article "Right in prison: Institutional police, juridical activism, democratic struggles" (roughly translated as "Right in prison: Institutional police, legal activism, democracy struggle"), author Gilles Chantraine; Dan Kaminski. In this article, the authors point out that prison sociology still has a lot of doubts about the real impact of criminal rights on the stewardship of the prisoner. The provision of offender rights will not limit the powers of prisons and the powers of administrators. The author argues that the prisoner's rights are understood to be a victory or, in other words, the ultimate benefit of a prison revolution. This is one of the social studies on prison law enforcement, its contributions show how different legal resources are mobilized to make the political struggle successful. against arbitrary actions in the prison. The solution is "penalty renewal", that is, a prison respects all human rights, the result of the change will create collective strength, aspiration to resist oppression. in the prison. Since then, it pressures the State to have an obligation in ensuring human rights for prisoners [139]. This is a very useful reference for the study of theoretical content in the research topic.

In addition, the study author has consulted a number of foreign experts' works such as: the book "The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights: Cases, Materials and Commentary" (International Covenant on Civil Rights and Politics: Cases, Documents and Comments) by the authors group including Sarah Joseph, Jenny Schults and Melissa Castan (Oxford University Press, Second Edition, 2004) [154]. The book "Protecting the right to a fair trial under the European Convention on Human Rights" by Dovydas Vitkauskas, Grigoriy Dikov, European Commission - Strasbourg, 2012 [140]. The book "The principle of equality of arms - part of the right to fair trial" by Elisa Toma [136]. Article "Mental Health care in prison" by John Reed, Journal of Psychiatry, Royal College of Psychiatry, London, UK, April 2003. Article "Using International Human Rights Laws and Standards for US Prison Reform "(Using international human rights laws and standards to reform American prisons) by Alvin J. Bronstein, Jenni Grainsborough, Pace Law Journal No. 811, Washington, USA, May 2004 [128]. Finally, in addition to the above mentioned sources, a number of other international human rights instruments (conventions, declarations, resolutions ...) of the United Nations agencies and other international organizations are also available. NCS reference and use to analyze.

2.2. The group has researched the current situation on ensuring human rights in the execution of imprisonment penalty

First of all, we can refer to the book "Capitalist Punishment: Prison Privatization & Human Rights" by Andrew Coyle, Allison Campbell, Rodney Neufeld - Clarity Press, 2003. The book focuses on clarifying the privatization of prisons, statistics show that more than 100,000 people in the United States are currently incarcerated in prisons owned and operated by public officials. private companies, but this phenomenon is not limited to the US, private prisons have been opened in Great Britain, Australia and New Zealand. Most recently, they have been known in Canada and South Africa, and are in the process of making a transition to developing countries. The private prison form was started in the 1980s, only a few countries participated and they were still in the experimental phase, the United States was the first model. Proponents of the private prison model have

argued that the adoption of the model is plausible and of great significance. They argue that adopting private prisons reduces costs from the budget to governments, services are better provided and more cost-effective for prisoners, and increases security for those living in communities. the area where the prison is located. However, most of the evidence in this book does not support their argument. Instead, it shows reduced security, poor employment standards, and inadequate protection of the offender's human rights. The first chapters define the United States' experience with privatization in prisons. In chapter I, the author points out that prisons privatization is part of the development of the "prison industrial cluster". This is a term used to describe the diversified developments in the US criminal justice system as an industry [131]. The book is a useful document to provide new perspectives on detention management for inmates in prisons, thereby helping the graduate student apply a comparison with the current situation of criminal management in Vietnam.

A very important book related to the topic to be mentioned is the monograph "Prisoners' Rights: Principles and Practice", the author. Susan Easton - Routledge, 2011. This book deals with the treatment of inmates in the United States, Great Britain and the Netherlands, and despite their different history, culture and social background, there are problems. politics is similar in maintaining integration and stability when prisoners are discriminated against in society [155].

In order to refer to the provisions of the laws of the countries of the world on the rights of prisoners, the book "A Compendium of Comparative Prison Legislation" (roughly translated as "Comprehensive study of the law on imprisonment penalty") by the Penal Reform International (Penal Reform International) published in 2008 is a document difficult to ignore. The book introduces the basic rights groups of offenders in criminal law in many countries, but focuses mainly on South Africa, Canada and Germany. This is considered an important document for graduate students to select and study the laws of different countries in order to bring a more comprehensive and objective view in assessing the legal status of Vietnam [148].

During the research, the graduate student also referred to the article "Latino / as and U.S. Prisons "(roughly translated as" The Prison System in America and Latino ") by José Luis Morín, in Behind Bars, edited by Suzanne Oboler, Palgrave Macmillan Press, New York, 2009. The book gives readers a certain understanding of the law of the United States as a country with the largest prison system and the largest proportion of prisoners in the world. When learning about US law, the graduate student also consulted articles in the journal Yale University and the US Criminal Law to gain more understanding of some of the limitations in ensuring criminal rights. This is the basis for the assessment of the status of ensuring the rights of prisoners in Vietnam compared to some countries, thereby helping to make recommendations to improve the current legal provisions on imprisonment in Vietnam. ensuring human rights in general and ensuring human rights in the execution of imprisonment penalty in particular [145].

In fact, people still believe that people are sentenced to prison and go to prison as punishment. The 2014 Human Rights and Respect in Prisons: The Prisoners' Perspective article by Bronwyn Naylor, 2014, points out the real situation in prisons activity, based on interviews conducted in several Australian prisons. The article emphasizes respect and recognition of human dignity, as an important foundation for those involved in detention and rehabilitation. With a wide research scope, covering all fields of imprisonment enforcement activities, this is an essential reference for the research and assessment of the current situation and proposing solutions of the research topic. rescue [133].

The monograph "A Human Rights Approach to Prison Management" (roughly translated as "Approaching human rights from the perspective of prison management") by Andrew Coyle, 2009. The book's content refers to exercise the prisoners' right to freedom of belief and religion during the sentence execution process. The author argues that this is a very important right and should be given facilitating attention from detention facilities. Accordingly, the prisons must arrange places where inmates can participate in religious activities such as praying, praying, and meeting religious representatives. In addition, in the book's content, the author gives a lot of solutions to improve the quality of management, detention of prisoners and guarantee their human rights.

Some typical solutions can be mentioned such as the proposal to cancel the detention in the disciplinary room to avoid negative impacts on the offender's psychology; propose detention in prisons near home to facilitate visit as well as encourage prisoners to voluntarily execute sentences, soon to be released [130]. This is a very useful reference for assessing the current legal situation and proposing solutions for your research.

It can be affirmed that in the world, human rights in the execution of imprisonment sentences, or the rights of prisoners are taken care of, acknowledged and guaranteed. Although the number of research works in this field is not many, it is not popular worldwide, but has made significant contributions to promote the recognition, guarantee and development of rights. the person who serves the sentence. In particular, the research results are an important theoretical and practical basis for the research author to research on human rights in the enforcement of imprisonment penalty in Vietnam.

3. Research method

To do the research, the Study also uses many traditional research methods, namely the following methods:

- Analytical method: is used to analyze and explain theoretical issues, the current state of legal regulations on human rights assurance in the execution of imprisonment penalty, arguments about solutions to enhance security. human rights in the execution of the imprisonment penalty.
- Systematic method: Used in many different stages in the research implementation process. In the first step, it is used to systematize documents, works, articles to overview the research situation and issues to be studied in the topic.
- The synthesis method: is used for the purpose of collecting and processing in a reasonable and effective manner relevant practical data which are meaningful for interpretation and clarification. research content.
- Historical method: It is used to learn the provisions of the law and the process of amending and supplementing Vietnam's criminal judgment enforcement law on ensuring human rights of prisoners over time. The author applies when studying the ideas and theories.
- Comparative method: It is used to compare changes in attitudes, perceptions and thoughts on ensuring human rights in the execution of imprisonment penalty through each stage, each criminal legal document, denunciation. Criminal proceedings and criminal judgment serving the specific purposes of the study.
- Statistical method: Used in statistics, clarifying the reality of ensuring human rights in the execution of imprisonment penalty.
- Typical research method: Used when studying some typical perspectives and theories on ensuring human rights in the execution of imprisonment penalty.
- Methods of sociological investigation: Used through the construction of questionnaires, questionnaires to collect opinions for the research process. This method has scientific predictive significance, in order to forecast development trends in rights and human rights requirements in the implementation of imprisonment penalty in Vietnam in the near future.
- Expert method: Used to assess human rights guarantee in imprisonment penalty execution

In addition, the study also uses a number of multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches to jurisprudence, other studies of human rights law and criminal judgment law, including: Inductive method and interpretation, descriptive methods, and also using other methods such as: Document research method, data, related research works, method of summarizing practical experience, method of analysis document analysis, interview methods, observation methods ... to select scientific knowledge and experience at home and abroad.

4. Result

Although the regime of communicating, communicating, meeting, sending gifts and receiving gifts from inmates in prisons, has strictly followed the legal policies, there are still some problems and violations. The visiting area in the prisons is still temporary, has not been provided with adequate equipment, ensuring the aesthetics of environmental hygiene as well as the request for visits. In addition, through direct interviews with a number of inmates at Xuan Ha Detention Center, many inmates and family members' feedback about the situation that it is difficult to check and control things brought into the prison. Communication between inmates' families and prisons is still lacking. Some prisons do not perform this function almost exclusively unless the offender dies or becomes seriously ill.

Table 1: Statistics on the regime of visiting relatives, contacting by phone of inmates in prisons under the Ministry of Public Security (from 2010 to 2018)

Year	Total number of prisoners	Total number of visits	1 hour visit	More hour visit	Contact by phone
2010	100662	435531	390453	43078	318630
2011	107900	435074	389838	45236	345751
2012	121686	418075	375107	42968	315237
2013	126729	510263	465969	44294	420336
2014	142342	712319	649599	62720	501795
2015	126934	724792	681994	42798	813675
2016	133936	706430	667050	39380	865031
2017	136777	684830	642728	42102	903496
2018	128916	557992	520395	37597	849000

Source: THAHS & HTTP Police General Department - Ministry of Public Security

The law requires an average of one prisoner to see their relatives at least once a month, but according to the statistics in the table above, the total number of visits is only 4 to 7 times more than the number of prisoners. On average, each inmate has 4-6 visits to meet, mainly overtime visits. The number of visits has increased from 2010 to 2018, specifically in 2010, there were 435,531 direct visits and 318,630 phone contacts out of a total of 100,662 prisoners (On average, each prisoner had 4.33 visits. face-to-face meetings, and 3.2 phone calls per year). In 2017, there were 684830 face-to-face visits and 903,496 phone contacts out of a total of 136,777 prisoners. According to the results of direct interviews, the cause of this situation comes from the visiting conditions of the inmates' families such as economic and geographical conditions, so the visits are often not used up. visit allowed by law. There are still many shortcomings in organizing visits from detention facilities, in some prisons the schedule of visits for offenders' families still depends on the Camp's schedule.

The regime of visiting, meeting and contacting relatives can be said to be implemented quite fully and seriously because of the clear and specific provisions of the law. However, in reality, it is necessary to propagate and disseminate relevant regulations to be understood and implemented more fully by the offenders themselves. In fact, these rights are basic rights and must be exercised, but there is still a "ask, give" mechanism every time we visit, meet or contact. It is necessary to create a positive change in awareness and action for staff who perform this task through the mechanism of monitoring, checking and evaluating according to the level of satisfaction, dissatisfaction with the detention facilities. detention of relatives in order to promote democracy while at the same time enhancing the role and responsibility of detention staff and detention facilities.

In recent times, many prisons have tried and made efforts to conduct special amnesty, reduce the term of serving sentences, and release prisons ahead of their conditional terms. With the criteria of open and transparent implementation, the special amnesty, the consideration of reducing the term of serving the imprisonment sentence are always conducted strictly and strictly according to the right subjects, not omitting the qualified person, and at the same time persistent. decided not to let the negativity happen. Conditions for consideration of

special amnesty, reduction of term, and premature release of prison are publicly posted for inmates to learn, comment on and vote on. The list of inmates who are proposed for special amnesty, reduction or conditional parole consideration is publicly posted so that inmates can compare and compare to ensure their rights and interests, and at the same time inspect and supervise. with the work of the agency responsible for enforcement.

In fact, the effective implementation of these institutions has created a strong impact in promoting and encouraging inmates to actively emulate, practice and progress to soon enjoy the leniency policy. of the Party and State. The review rounds, special amnesty have all met the requirements of politics, social order and received great consent and support from inmates serving sentences and the public. At the same time, the special amnesty, the reduction of the penalty term, and the conditional release of prison also contribute to reducing the state budget costs, reducing the pressure on the prisons, creating favorable conditions for prisons to improve. providing equipment and facilities, thereby improving the quality of education, improving prisoners, preparing necessary conditions for prisoners to be able to reimburse wages and reintegrate into the community.

Table 2. Statistics on the reduction of imprisonment sentences and special amnesty in prisons under the Ministry of Public Security (2010-2018)

Year	Total number of prisoners	Considering reduction of imprisonment term	Special amnesty
2010	100.662	58.456	17.210
2011	107.900	53.498	10.535
2012	121.686	59.016	0
2013	126.729	66.034	15.446
2014	142.342	70.532	11
2015	126.934	78.274	18.298
2016	133.936	75.285	4.179
2017	136.777	82.377	0
2018	128.916	88.006	0

Source: THAHS & HTTP Police General Department - Ministry of Public Security

According to statistics from the Ministry of Public Security from 2010 to 2018, the President has issued six decisions on special amnesty for major holidays and major events of the country, totaling 65,679. The prisoner serving his sentence was granted special amnesty during that time. The consideration of reducing the term of serving imprisonment sentences is conducted regularly, a large number of inmates receive a relatively equal average reduction from 40% to 70% of the total number of prisoners annually. For example, in 2010 there were 58,456 prisoners (accounting for 58%); in 2011 there were 53,498 prisoners

(occupy 50%); in 2012 there were 59,016 prisoners (accounting for 40%), in 2017 there were 82,377 prisoners (accounting for 60%); in 2018, there were 88,006 prisoners (accounting for 68%). This ratio not only proves the effectiveness of the special amnesty, reducing the time limit for serving the sentence, but also shows positive and positive results in the management and supervision in order to reimburse the executors, in association with Improving, educating is the respect to ensure the best human rights for prisoners.

Inspection and supervision to ensure human rights of prisoners are always focused and strictly implemented. In which, the Procuracy's supervision is a major and effective channel. The Supreme People's Procuracy issued Directive No. 06 / CT-VKSTC dated June 18, 2019 on renewing, improving the quality and efficiency of supervision of custody, detention and criminal judgment execution. . The directive requires People's Procuracies at all levels to strengthen the supervision of detention facilities, renovate and promptly handle violations to ensure the legitimate interests of the judgment executors.

People's Procuracies at all levels have taken measures to perform their tasks and functions such as adhering to the program, work plan content, management, monitoring, and serious implementation of the professional regulations. carry out the prosecution at detention facilities according to planned targets and take prompt impact

measures; conduct regular and quarterly thematic inspections, a comprehensive inspection for six months and a year, from which step by step improve the quality of inspection and supervision. At the same time, the Procuracy also strengthened ad-hoc inspection and supervision activities, coordinated with the Fatherland Fronts of the same level on a regular and irregular basis to inspect the activities of prisons, to bring the work of supervision over the years. Recently, the quality has been improved and many encouraging results have been achieved.

According to the table of statistics, the Procuracy organizes direct supervision of prisons, inmates management sub-camps at prisons. Through supervisory activities have discovered and issued protests and recommendations to request judgment enforcement agencies to terminate and handle violations to best ensure the interests of judgment executors. . According to criminal judgment execution statistics, in 2018, the Supreme People's Procuracy conducted direct prosecution of 136 times in detention centers, 109 times in detention centers. The results of the prosecution show that, during the family time, the prisons basically strictly implemented. Issuing 166 preventive petitions for detention centers (of which 166 were accepted) and 58 petitions were accepted. for prison (of which 57 petitions were accepted). The contents of the protests and petitions have been received, corrected and overcome. The results of the supervisory work have had a positive impact on the prison sentence enforcement activities, the management of prisons across the country has been strengthened and paid more attention than before; shortcomings in this work are also promptly overcome; from there, to ensure that the supervision and education of prisoners are carried out in accordance with the law, and the regime for prisoners is strictly observed.

Table 3: Statistics on criminal judgment enforcement activities of the Supreme People's Procuracy (2015-2018)

Criteria	2015		2016		2017		2018	
	<i>n</i> Detentio	Prison	<i>n</i> Detentio	Prison	<i>n</i> Detentio	Prison	<i>n</i> Detentio	Prison
Direct inspection	185	93	158	96	167	89	136	109
Request	67	51	64	43	127	37	166	58
The petition is accepted	65	46	50	36	127	32	166	57

(Source: Supreme People's Procuracy)

Supervision by the Fatherland Front Committee also plays an important role in ensuring human rights of prisoners in prisons. Over the past years, the coordination between the Fatherland Front Committee at the same level in the province and the People's Procuracy system has been constantly strengthened and consolidated. In good implementation of Plan 83 / KH-V4, the Fatherland Front Committee performs its supervisory function of law observance in detention facilities, in order to improve quality and effectiveness. results of supervisory work, ensuring the interests and regimes of judgment executors. Within the scope of its functions and duties, the Fatherland Front Committee has coordinated with other agencies to promptly and strictly detect and handle law violations in the management and detention of prisoners. ; The Fatherland Front Committee has participated in many direct inspections of news reports, criminal denunciations, coordinated monitoring and direct detention supervision, and issued many petitions.

Inspection and supervision of the People's Councils at all levels are conducted regularly according to annual plans and specific topics. Recommendations have been promptly made through supervisory activities, contributing to improving efficiency in ensuring human rights. The follow-up after monitoring was also strengthened, to promptly urge the resolution of recommendations of the competent authorities.

In general, the inspection and supervision mechanism of agencies with respect to implementation, ensuring human rights in our country in detention facilities has generally been clearly and specifically defined by law. However, in reality, the inspection is still formalistic, not comprehensive and in depth. Because, the inspection

of specialized agencies (such as the VKS) or periodic inspection such as the People's Council ... is still subject to the constraints of the working relationship mechanism, coordination relationship, and reporting processing, self-reporting, preparation ... Therefore, in order to ensure the inspection and supervision of agencies for this work, it is necessary to clearly define the independent monitoring mechanism, transparency and ensuring democracy and objectivity.

5. Conclusion

With flexible policies, improving quality as well as innovating methods, suitable to the conditions and circumstances in the new situation, the management and education of prisoners have achieved many positive results, making an important contribution to the education and rehabilitation of criminals to become useful people for the society when they reintegrate into the community. Through sensitization, education and persuasion, inmates have many positive changes in their ideology as well as awareness of their mistakes and mistakes, thereby obeying the rules and regulations of the Prison. In order to fulfill their obligations well, the prisons have taken many positive measures to direct and assign full-time cadres to firmly grasp and strictly abide by the Party's undertakings, guidelines and policies. and the State's laws on imprisonment penalty enforcement. The Prisons use appropriate measures to effectively apply sensitization to each prisoner; With the aim, through management and education, prisoners can see the leniency policy of the Party and State, grasp their rights and obligations, thereby voluntarily complying with them.

From the reality of ensuring human rights in the execution of imprisonment sentences in Vietnam, it has been pointed out that: the basic human rights of prisoners are getting more and more attention, relevant regulations on imprisonment execution are basically strictly and unified by the executing agencies and organizations; rights and interests of prisoners are basically fully realized. During the period from 2010 to 2018, the management of detention, detention, and education of prisoners was carried out in accordance with the law, achieved many positive results, contributing an important role in ensuring security. , safe for inmates in Prisons. Inmates' diets, clothing and accommodation are seriously and fully implemented, ensuring proper quantitative standards in order to ensure the health of the prisoners during the execution of sentences. Inmates have basic learning and labor organizations that are suitable and meet the requirements of management, education and rehabilitation goals. The content of the educational programs for prisoners is always interested, innovated in terms of form, method as well as content. The leaders of the prisons have clearly defined their main task is to educate and reform, thereby fundamentally changing in terms of awareness and judgment execution attitude of inmates in a positive direction, helping them early. become a useful person to society. At the same time, the staff of the Prisons are fully identified and aware of their responsibilities and attitudes in the process of dealing with and dealing with prisoners, minimizing negative behaviors and harassment. Do not allow assaults, harm to life, health, or lives or cases of prisoners getting sick, sick or depleted during the time of serving sentences.

The results achieved in the management and education of prisoners are the result of trying, complying and strictly implementing the provisions of relevant laws of agencies, organizations and individuals in the enforcement of a prison sentence. In addition to the achieved results, judgment enforcement from the perspective of ensuring human rights over the years still has some shortcomings, shortcomings and limitations.

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